

Proposal for curricula on In Silico Trials

The proposal for curricula is based on the intended learning outcomes (ILOs) for the different stakeholders published by Vander Linden et al. [1].

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1. Training

1.1. MS in Biomedical Engineering

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.2 Solve linear algebra and geometry problems numerically
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data

And to a lesser extent of consensus:

- H 1.1.4 Solve differential equations numerically
- H 1.1.6 Solve optimisation problems numerically

Inclusions in existing modules: Physics and chemistry

While the fundamentals of mechanics, inorganic chemistry and electromagnetism should be known, in all modules, an effort should be made to embed the following:

- H 1.2.1 Use Newtonian mechanics laws to solve problems
- H 1.2.2 Use thermodynamics and chemistry laws to solve problems
- H 1.2.3 Use electromagnetism laws to solve problems

Inclusions in existing modules: Bioengineering

The bioengineering module(s) should include the following ILOs:

- H 1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H 1.4.5 Biophysics: apply physics laws to the solution of biomedical problems

Inclusions in existing modules: Computer science

A full module on computational sciences is probably not justified. However, other modules should include the following ILO, possibly in a new module of computational bioengineering or of *in silico* medicine:

- H 1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)

New module: Introduction to in silico medicine

This additional module could be optional to all MS students in biomedical engineering and mandatory for those who choose the specialisation *in silico* medicine. In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of *in silico* methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to *in silico* methodologies in communication
- H 2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of *in silico* methodologies in communication
- H 2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of *in silico* methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H 3.1 Survey the practice of *in silico* medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H 3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
- H 3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
- H 4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of *in vitro*, animal, or human experimentation
- H 4.14 Use *in silico* methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy and evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Introduction to *In Silico* Medicine could be designed as a classic 6 ECTS module, with a total student commitment of 150 hours, of which 24 hours are frontal teaching, 48 hours are laboratory teaching, and the rest is personal study. The 12 two-hour lectures could include, for example, the following:

- M1-L01 Introduction to *in silico* medicine: can nature be predicted?
- M1-L02 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare (H2.1)

- M1-L03 In Silico Medicine: ethical and legal considerations (H3.1)
- M1-L04 Regulatory and standardisation aspects (H3.4.1, H3.4.2)
- M1-L05 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro* experimentation (H4.1)
- M1-L06 Examples of in silico medicine: reduction of animal experimentation (H4.1)
- M1-L07 Examples of in silico medicine: refinement of human experimentation (H4.1)
- M1-L08 In Silico Trials for medical devices (H.4.14)
- M1-L09 In Silico Trials for medicinal products (H.4.14)
- M1-L10 Communication in interdisciplinary settings (H2.2, H2.3, H2.11)
- M1-L11 Clinical applications of In Silico Medicine
- M1-L12 Industrial applications of In Silico Medicine

New module: Computational Bioengineering

Also, this additional module could be optional to all MS students in biomedical engineering and mandatory for those who choose the specialisation *in silico* medicine. In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2 Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H5 Develop In Silico Methodologies
 - H 5.4.1 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Machine Learning models
 - H 5.4.6 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Stochastic models
 - H 5.4.7 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Optimisation models
 - H 5.5 Develop a data-driven model:
 - H 5.5.1 Collect and properly organise data
 - H 5.5.2 Curate data
 - H 5.5.4 Train the model
 - H 5.5.5 Evaluate and tune the model on the training set
 - H 5.5.6 Validate the model on test sets
 - H 5.6 Develop a knowledge-driven model:
 - H 5.6.3 Formulate the model in terms of idealisations
 - H 5.6.11 Conduct initial validation to confirm the model's design choices

Computational Bioengineering could be designed as a classic 6 ECTS module, with a total student commitment of 150 hours, of which 24 hours of frontal teaching, 48 hours of laboratory teaching, and the rest of personal study. The 12 two-hour lectures could include, for example, the following:

- M2-L01 Recalls of human pathophysiology (H1.3.1)
- M2-L02 Recalls of biophysics (H1.3.2)
- M2-L03 Recalls of biochemistry (H1.3.2)
- M2-L04 Recalls of numerical analysis
- M2-L05 Stochastic modelling
- M2-L06 Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part 1

- M2-L08 Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part 2
- M2-L09 Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part 1
- M2-L10 Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part 2
- M2-L11 Development of a In Silico Trials solutions
- M2-L12 Credibility of predictive models

1.2. MS in Computational Bioengineering

As the field expands, some large universities might have opportunities to develop a specialised curriculum. We assume a conventional 2-year, 120 ECTS master's degree.

Pre-requisite Intended Learning Outcomes

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.2 Solve linear algebra and geometry problems numerically
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.4 Solve differential equations numerically
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.6 Solve optimisation problems numerically
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data

The course structure is similar to a conventional MS in biomedical engineering:

#	Module title	ECTS	#	Optional Modules
1	Physiology	6	1	Medical Informatics
2	Biology	6	2	Digital and mobile Health
3	Biochemistry	6	3	Biomedical data science
4	Biomechanics	6	4	Machine Learning in medicine
5	Bioelectromagnetism	6	5	Bioinformatics and computational biochemistry
6	Numerical analysis	6	6	Computational musculoskeletal biomechanics
7	Biostatistics	6	7	Computational cardiovascular biomechanics
8	Computational Science & engineering	6	8	Computational neuroscience
9	Biomedical Instrumentation	6	9	Computational immunology and oncology
10	Biomedical signal processing	6	10	Computational pharmacology
11	Biomedical Imaging	6		
12	Biological systems modelling	6		
13	Introduction to in silico medicine	6		
14	Optional module	6		
15	Optional module	6		
16	Optional module	6		
17	Optional module	6		
18	Optional module	6		
20	Final examination (thesis)	12		
	TOTAL CREDITS	120		

In the first year, in addition to the fundamentals in physiology, biology, biochemistry, biomechanics, and bio-electromagnetism, we also provide some elements of biostatistics and numerical analysis, which are required in the other modules. Computational Science & Engineering focus on more specialised aspects of numerical modelling, including computer architectures and programming languages. This is followed by a core of traditional biomedical engineering modules (instrumentation, signals, imaging) and a first introduction to modelling biological systems. In the second year, in addition to an introductory course in in silico medicine (possibly the same detailed below in addition to an MS in Biomedical Engineering), five optional modules, chosen from a list of ten, and the final examination.

1.3. PhD in Biomedical Engineering

Intended learning outcomes

Contrary to MS programs, the structure of PhD programs varies considerably from country to country and, in some cases, even between universities in the same country. In some cases, the training is primarily by research, and frontal teaching is marginal; in others, there are structured teaching modules for PhD students. Thus, we can only provide considerations on the ILOs; how to achieve them varies depending on the structure of the doctoral program.

Most of the ILOs we identified are considered necessary at the PhD level. We list here those the experts considered less useful:

- H 1.3.4 Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs
- H 2.4 Collect and use key concepts on economic risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 3.6.1 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the regulatory qualification of in silico methodologies
- H 3.6.2 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the marketing authorisation for in silico methodologies
- H 3.6.3 Use regulatory knowledge to implement a total lifecycle-based framework for AI-based in silico methodologies
- H 4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report
- H 4.12 Position the adopted in silico methodology in the product life cycle
- H 4.13 Conduct impact analysis on the deployment of in silico methodologies in a clinical setting
- H 6.3 Develop documentation to describe and qualify for in silico methodologies
- H 6.6 Assess, plan, implement and review good simulation practice

1.4. MS in Life Science

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.2 Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H 1.3.4 Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs
- H 1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

New module: Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers with a focus on bioinformatics

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H 1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)
- H 1.5.4 Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)
- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H 4.14 Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers could be designed as a classic 6 ECTS module, with a total student commitment of 150 hours, of which 24 hours are frontal teaching, 48 hours are laboratory teaching, and the rest is personal study. The 12 two-hour lectures could include, for example, the following:

- M3-L01 Introduction to bioinformatics part 1 (H 1.5.1, H 1.5.4)
- M3-L02 Introduction to bioinformatics part 2 (H 1.5.1, H 1.5.4)
- M3-L03 Introduction to bioengineering part 1 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)
- M3-L04 Introduction to bioengineering part 2 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)

- M3-L05 Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?
- M3-L06 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare (H2.1)
- M3-L07 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M3-L08 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M3-L09 In Silico Trials for medical devices (H.4.14)
- M3-L10 In Silico Trials for medicinal devices (H.4.14)
- M3-L11 In Silico Medicine: ethical and social considerations (H2.5, H2.6)
- M3-L12 Communication in interdisciplinary settings (H2.2)

It should be noted that Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers with a focus on bioinformatics has only minor differences from the Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers for the MS in Medicine (see below). One could consider designing a single course that serves life science and medicine degrees in universities where the numbers need to be larger, and with a bit more tweaking, to extend it to Allied Health Professions.

1.5. MS in Medicine

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.2 Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H 1.3.4 Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs

New module: Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H 1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H 2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs
- H 4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

This module could be designed as a 3 ECTS module, with a total student commitment of 100 hours, of which 12 hours are frontal teaching, 12 hours are laboratory teaching, and the rest is personal study. The 12 one-hour lectures could include, for example, the following:

- M4-L01 Recall concepts of biostatistics (H 1.3.5, H 1.1.7)
- M4-L02 Recall concepts of biostatistics (H 1.3.5, H 1.1.7)
- M4-L03 Introduction to bioengineering part 1 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)
- M4-L04 Introduction to bioengineering part 2 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)
- M4-L05 Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?

- M4-L06 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare (H2.1)
- M4-L07 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M4-L08 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M4-L09 Clinical applications of In Silico Medicine (H2.12)
- M4-L10 In Silico Medicine: ethical and social considerations (H2.5, H2.6)
- M4-L11 Communication in interdisciplinary settings (H2.2)
- M4-L12 Communication to patients (H2.8)

1.6. MS in Allied Health Professions

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.2 Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases

Inclusions in the module Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H 2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

2. Retraining

2.1 Biomedical Industry – Research & Development

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the researchers should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the ‘Small Private Online Course’ (SPOC) *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.2 Solve linear algebra and geometry problems numerically
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.4 Solve differential equations numerically
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.6 Solve optimisation problems numerically
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2 Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H1.4.5 Biophysics: apply physics laws to the solution of biomedical problems
- H1.4.6 Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro, or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)
- H1.5.2 Program algorithms using computationally efficient compiled programming languages and specialised libraries (C++, Fortran)
- H1.5.4 Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.7 Collect and use a portfolio of success stories for in silico methodologies to achieve effective communication
- H2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers

- H2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.2 Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.3 Design the study involving in silico methodologies, define the Context of Use
- H4.4 Conduct risk analysis according to the ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.5 Define the VVUQ plan according to ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.6 Collect evidence of, or conduct, code verification
- H4.7 Conduct calculation verification
- H4.8 Conduct uncertainty quantification studies
- H4.9 Design validation experiments in vitro, on animals or on humans
- H4.10 Report credibility assessment of an in silico methodology according to ASME VV-40
- H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report
- H4.12 Position the adopted in silico methodology in the product life cycle
- H4.13 Conduct impact analysis on the deployment of in silico methodologies in a clinical setting
- H4.14 Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

SPOC module: Develop In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H5.1 Translate unmet needs into specifications for an in silico trial solution
- H5.2 Develop data management methodologies respectful of ethical, legal, and procedural constraints
- H5.3 Develop synthetic clinical data collections from existing collections of clinical data
- H5.4 Select data-driven, knowledge-driven, or a combination of modelling methods based on the availability of annotated data and of reliable mechanistic knowledge on the mechanism of action of the class of diagnostics or interventions being modelled; on the natural history of the disease; on the underlying physiology
- H5.4.1 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Machine Learning models
- H5.4.2 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Deep Learning models
- H5.4.3 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biochemistry models
- H5.4.4 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biophysics models
- H5.4.5 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Agent-based models
- H5.4.6 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Stochastic models
- H5.4.7 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Optimisation models
- H5.5 Develop a data-driven model:
 - H5.5.1 Collect and properly organise data

- H5.5.2 Curate data
- H5.5.3 Choose the appropriate model or explore transfer learning
- H5.5.4 Train the model
- H5.5.5 Evaluate and tune the model on the training set
- H5.5.6 Validate the model on test sets
- H5.6 Develop a knowledge-driven model:
 - H5.6.1 Collect and properly organise available mechanistic knowledge on treatment, disease, and physiology, using appropriate standards and tools
 - H5.6.2 Formulate the model in terms of inputs and outputs; identify patient-specific and population-specific inputs
 - H5.6.3 Formulate the model in terms of idealisations
 - H5.6.4 Formulate the mathematical model
 - H5.6.5 Select the best numerical method to solve the mathematical model
 - H5.6.6 Make or Buy – select the best tools to develop the model, also in the light of code verification
 - H5.6.7 Collect and curate the input data
 - H5.6.8 Develop all pre-processing steps to transform the available data into valid inputs, including the generation of virtual patients / virtual cohorts
 - H5.6.9 Develop the model and run preliminary solution verification tests
 - H5.6.10 Conduct parameters sweep and sensitivity analysis
 - H5.6.11 Conduct initial validation to confirm the model’s design choices

SPOC module: Apply good simulation practice

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H6.1 Find up-to-date guidelines, technical standards, and regulations related to good simulation practice
- H6.2 Apply best practices in data collection, data management, provision of synthetic datasets, data curation and processing
- H6.3 Develop documentation to describe and qualify for in silico methodologies
- H6.4 Apply Good Laboratory Practice and Good Clinical Practice to conduct laboratory or clinical validation studies
- H6.5 Manage all credibility assessment activities according to established good simulation practice
- H6.6 Assess, plan, implement and review good simulation practice
- H6.7 Use independent datasets (including synthetic) for calibration and validation

2.2 Biomedical Industry – Regulatory & Quality

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the researchers should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.4.6 Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro, or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)

SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.4 Collect and use key concepts on economic risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.7 Collect and use a portfolio of success stories for in silico methodologies to achieve effective communication
- H2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H2.9 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to policy-makers
- H2.10 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to medical professionals
- H2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles

- H3.2 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.3 Develop data management plans for sensitive data with the help of cybersecurity and legal experts
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
 - H3.4.3 Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence
- H3.5 Pursue the approval of an Ethical Review Board for animal and human studies for the validation or the use of in silico methodologies
- H3.6 Use the knowledge of EU and US regulatory systems for medical products to achieve specific regulatory objectives
 - H3.6.1 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the regulatory qualification of in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.2 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the marketing authorisation for in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.3 Use regulatory knowledge to implement a total lifecycle-based framework for AI-based in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, this is necessary:

- H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report

2.4 Precompetitive – biomedical researchers

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the researchers should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2 Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H1.3.4 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.6 Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H 1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)
- H 1.5.4 Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H2.10 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to medical professionals
- H2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.3 Develop data management plans for sensitive data with the help of cybersecurity and legal experts
- H3.5 Pursue the approval of an Ethical Review Board for animal and human studies for the validation or the use of in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.2 Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.3 Design the study involving in silico methodologies, define the Context of Use
- H4.4 Conduct risk analysis according to the ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.9 Design validation experiments in vitro, on animals or on humans
- H4.10 Report credibility assessment of an in silico methodology according to ASME VV-40
- H4.14 Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

2.5 Precompetitive – health technology researchers

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the researchers should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2 Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H1.4.5 Biophysics: apply physics laws to the solution of biomedical problems
- H1.4.6 Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H1.5.1 Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)
- H1.5.3 Program algorithms to be batch-executed on time-sharing parallel or distributed computer systems (HPC, Cloud computing)
- H1.5.4 Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.7 Collect and use a portfolio of success stories for in silico methodologies to achieve effective communication
- H2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H2.10 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to medical professionals
- H2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.3 Develop data management plans for sensitive data with the help of cybersecurity and legal experts
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
- H3.5 Pursue the approval of an Ethical Review Board for animal and human studies for the validation or the use of in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.2 Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.3 Design the study involving in silico methodologies, define the Context of Use
- H4.4 Conduct risk analysis according to the ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.5 Define the VVUQ plan according to ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.6 Collect evidence of, or conduct, code verification
- H4.7 Conduct calculation verification
- H4.8 Conduct uncertainty quantification studies
- H4.9 Design validation experiments in vitro, on animals or on humans
- H4.10 Report credibility assessment of an in silico methodology according to ASME VV-40
- H4.14 Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

SPOC module: Develop In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H5.1 Translate unmet needs into specifications for an in silico trial solution
- H5.2 Develop data management methodologies respectful of ethical, legal, and procedural constraints
- H5.3 Develop synthetic clinical data collections from existing collections of clinical data
- H5.4 Select data-driven, knowledge-driven, or a combination of modelling methods based on the availability of annotated data and of reliable mechanistic knowledge on the mechanism of action of the class of diagnostics or interventions being modelled; on the natural history of the disease; on the underlying physiology
 - H5.4.1 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Machine Learning models
 - H5.4.2 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Deep Learning models

- H5.4.3 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biochemistry models
- H5.4.4 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biophysics models
- H5.4.5 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Agent-based models
- H5.4.6 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Stochastic models
- H5.4.7 Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Optimisation models
- H5.5 Develop a data-driven model:
 - H5.5.1 Collect and properly organise data
 - H5.5.2 Curate data
 - H5.5.3 Choose the appropriate model or explore transfer learning
 - H5.5.4 Train the model
 - H5.5.5 Evaluate and tune the model on the training set
 - H5.5.6 Validate the model on test sets
- H5.6 Develop a knowledge-driven model:
 - H5.6.1 Collect and properly organise available mechanistic knowledge on treatment, disease, and physiology, using appropriate standards and tools
 - H5.6.2 Formulate the model in terms of inputs and outputs; identify patient-specific and population-specific inputs
 - H5.6.3 Formulate the model in terms of idealisations
 - H5.6.4 Formulate the mathematical model
 - H5.6.5 Select the best numerical method to solve the mathematical model
 - H5.6.6 Make or Buy – select the best tools to develop the model, also in the light of code verification
 - H5.6.7 Collect and curate the input data
 - H5.6.8 Develop all pre-processing steps to transform the available data into valid inputs, including the generation of virtual patients / virtual cohorts
 - H5.6.9 Develop the model and run preliminary solution verification tests
 - H5.6.10 Conduct parameters sweep and sensitivity analysis
 - H5.6.11 Conduct initial validation to confirm the model’s design choices

SPOC module: Apply good simulation practice

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H6.1 Find up-to-date guidelines, technical standards, and regulations related to good simulation practice
- H6.2 Apply best practices in data collection, data management, provision of synthetic datasets, data curation and processing
- H6.3 Develop documentation to describe and qualify for in silico methodologies
- H6.4 Apply Good Laboratory Practice and Good Clinical Practice to conduct laboratory or clinical validation studies
- H6.5 Manage all credibility assessment activities according to established good simulation practice
- H6.6 Assess, plan, implement and review good simulation practice
- H6.7 Use independent datasets (including synthetic) for calibration and validation

2.6 Precompetitive – pharmacological researchers

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the researchers should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2 Apply knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H1.3.4 Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H1.4.6 Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H1.5.4 Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.10 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to medical professionals
- H2.11 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.3 Develop data management plans for sensitive data with the help of cybersecurity and legal experts
- H3.5 Pursue the approval of an Ethical Review Board for animal and human studies for the validation or the use of in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.3 Design the study involving in silico methodologies, define the Context of Use
- H4.4 Conduct risk analysis according to the ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.9 Design validation experiments in vitro, on animals or on humans
- H4.10 Report credibility assessment of an in silico methodology according to ASME VV-40
- H4.14 Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

2.7 Governmental agencies –health technology assessment bodies staff

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the staff should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.2 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
- H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
- H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
- H3.4.3 Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

- H4.2 Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report

2.8 Governmental agencies – regulators staff

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the staff should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.2 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
 - H3.4.3 Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence
- H3.6 Use the knowledge of EU and US regulatory systems for medical products to achieve specific regulatory objectives
 - H3.6.1 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the regulatory qualification of in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.2 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the marketing authorisation for in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.3 Use regulatory knowledge to implement a total lifecycle-based framework for AI-based in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report

References

[1] Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for In Silico Trials. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>.